

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

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ANALYSIS OF GREEN ECONOMIC GROWTH INDICATORS IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This article analyzes the current state of the green economy concept in Uzbekistan, its growth indicators, and mechanisms aimed at increasing these indicators. In the development of a green economy, environmental sustainability, rational use of resources, increasing energy efficiency, and the introduction of environmentally friendly technologies are of great importance. The article also develops strategic directions based on international experience and proposals that are appropriate for the conditions of Uzbekistan. The proposed mechanisms are aimed at ensuring a balance between economic growth and environmental safety.

Key words: Green economy, environmental sustainability, energy efficiency, sustainable development, economic mechanisms, environmental innovations, Uzbekistan, environmental policy.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada O'zbekistonda yashil iqtisodiyot konsepsiyasining hozirgi holati, uning o'sish ko'rsatkichlari va ushbu ko'rsatkichlarni oshirishga qaratilgan mexanizmlar tahlil qilinadi. Yashil iqtisodiyotni rivojlantirishda atrof-muhit barqarorligi, resurslardan oqilona foydalanish, energiya samaradorligini oshirish va ekologik toza texnologiyalarni joriy etish muhim ahamiyat kasb etadi. Maqolada, shuningdek, xalqaro tajriba asosida ishlab chiqilgan va O'zbekiston sharoitiga mos bo'lgan strategik yo'nalishlar va takliflar keltirilgan. Taklif etilgan mexanizmlar iqtisodiy o'sish bilan ekologik xavfsizlik o'rtasidagi muvozanatni ta'minlashga qaratilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: yashil iqtisodiyot, ekologik barqarorlik, energiya samaradorligi, barqaror rivojlanish, iqtisodiy mexanizmlar, ekologik innovatsiyalar, O'zbekiston, ekologik siyosat.

Аннотация: В данной статье анализируется текущее состояние концепции «зелёной экономики» в Узбекистане, показатели её роста и механизмы, направленные на их повышение. В развитии зелёной экономики особое значение придается экологической устойчивости, рациональному использованию ресурсов, повышению энергоэффективности и внедрению экологически чистых технологий. Также в статье разрабатываются стратегические направления и предложения, основанные на международном опыте и адаптированные к условиям Узбекистана. Предложенные механизмы направлены на обеспечение баланса между экономическим ростом и экологической безопасностью.

Ключевые слова: зелёная экономика, экологическая устойчивость, энергоэффективность, устойчивое развитие, экономические механизмы, экологические инновации, Узбекистан, экологическая политика.

INTRODUCTION

One of the most important global problems of the 21st century is ensuring environmental sustainability. Environmental threats arising from climate change, limited natural resources, environmental pollution, and demographic pressure require a fundamental rethinking of the economic development model. In these conditions, the concept of “green economy” is gaining relevance as an alternative direction of economic development based on environmental safety, social equality, and rational use of resources. This approach is

aimed at reducing the environmental burden along with economic growth, ensuring the restoration of natural resources, and improving living conditions for future generations.

The Republic of Uzbekistan has also identified the concept of green economy as a priority strategic direction in ensuring sustainable development. Certain work is being carried out in the country to expand the use of renewable energy sources, recycle waste, increase the efficiency of resource use, and introduce environmentally friendly technologies. However, effective management, a scientific approach, economic mechanisms, and comprehensive strategies based on international experience are important for the deep implementation of the principles of a green economy in practice.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study studied the state of development of the green economy in Uzbekistan based on a comprehensive approach. Several methods were used as a research methodology: conceptual foundations and theoretical approaches were analyzed based on international and national sources (literature analysis); a review of regulatory and legal documents was carried out based on the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-436 and strategic documents for 2019-2030; the economic efficiency of market mechanisms such as environmental taxes, carbon prices and quota trading introduced in other countries was assessed (comparative analysis); and the opportunities and risks of transitioning to a green economy in the country were identified based on available statistical and normative data (analytical approach). This approach allows developing strategies that are appropriate for national characteristics, taking into account international experience, in the process of transitioning to a green economy in Uzbekistan.

LITERATURE REVIEW ON THE TOPIC

An analysis of scientific literature on the concept of a green economy shows that foreign scientists have interpreted this concept in different ways. For example, D. Pearce (1989) describes the green economy as an economic model based on environmental criteria and advocates the need to integrate environmental calculations into economic policy. E. Barbier (2011) defines the green economy as a means of harmonizing economic growth with environmental health. M. Jacobs (1991) sees the green economy as a mechanism that ensures a balance between social justice and environmental sustainability. In addition, experts such as the UN Environment Program (UNEP, 2011), OECD, Costanza, Schmalensee propose ways to limit environmental degradation in the green economy through innovations, carbon taxes, and market-based approaches. Uzbek researchers have analyzed the concept of the green economy based on national conditions. In particular, I. Yuldashev evaluates the green economy as a strategy for the efficient use of resources and reducing environmental risks. M. Yuldashev interprets the green economy as a production model that is compatible with maintaining human health and ecological balance. Turaev Sh. links this approach to the efficient use of water in agriculture, while Karimov A. highlights the modernization of infrastructure and the transition to renewable energy as priorities. These approaches demonstrate that the idea of a green economy in Uzbekistan is increasingly integrated into national development strategies.

A green economy is a system that leads not only to environmental protection, but also to a specific transformation of the economy. Among the most important benefits of a green economy for Uzbekistan are the potential to reduce dependence on energy imports, increase water use efficiency in agriculture, create new jobs, and improve public health. At the same time, the lack of infrastructure, a weak technological base, and weak financing mechanisms can hinder the rapid development of a green economy.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

Although market mechanisms such as environmental taxes, carbon pricing, and emissions trading have yielded positive results abroad, their adaptation to the conditions of Uzbekistan must be carefully planned. A step-by-step approach is needed, taking into account the country's climate, economic structure, and the ability of the population to pay. From this point of view, one of the urgent tasks is to deeply integrate the concept of a green economy into the science and education system, to increase the national human resources capacity in this regard.

On October 5, 2019, the "Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for the Transition to a Green Economy in 2019–2030" was adopted. This strategy sets out areas such as integrating "green" principles into education and science, widespread introduction of renewable energy sources, increasing energy efficiency, and developing "clean" transport. On this basis, it is also envisaged to include the basics of a "green economy" in general education programs. Presidential Decree No. PQ-436, adopted on December 2, 2022, plans to achieve the following target indicators by 2030:

- reduce greenhouse gas emissions per unit of gross domestic product by 35 percent from 2010 levels;
- increase the production capacity of renewable energy sources by 15 GW and bring their share to more than 30 percent of the total volume of electricity generation;
- increase energy efficiency in the industrial sector by at least 20 percent;
- reduce energy consumption per unit of gross domestic product by 30 percent, including by expanding the use of renewable energy sources;
- significantly increase the efficiency of water use in all sectors of the economy, introduce water-saving irrigation technologies on an area of up to 1 million hectares;
- expanding green spaces in cities by more than 30 percent by planting 200 million seedlings per year and increasing the total number of seedlings to 1 billion;
- increasing the reserves of the republic's forest fund to more than 90 million cubic meters. Furthermore, based on international experience, there is a need to strengthen economic mechanisms in Uzbekistan by introducing environmental taxes, carbon pricing, and pollution quota trading. For example, in Sweden, the CO₂ tax amounts to \$139 per ton, while in the European Union, the price of CO₂ is set at around €90 under the emissions trading system. Such approaches make it possible to ensure environmental sustainability through economic incentives.

Table 1. Target indicators for the transition to a “green” economy and ensuring “green” growth in the Republic of Uzbekistan by 2030

№	Indicators	Unit of measurement	2022	2024	2026	2028	2030
1.	Reducing energy consumption per unit of GDP (compared to 2021)	%	5,0	14,0	22,0	27,0	30,0
2.	Electricity consumption in industry, share in total consumption	%	26,0	25,0	23,0	21,0	20,0
3.	Expanding the share of renewable energy sources in total electricity generation (including hydropower)	%	8,0	9,0	24,3	29,0	30,5
		kVt/s	6,5	8,6	25,0	34,0	40,7
4.	Construction of small-scale solar photovoltaic power plants	MVt	10,0	150,0	400,0	800,0	1500,0
5.	Population with access to improved drinking water sources, as a percentage of total population	%	69,7	80,93	87,12	88,5	90,0
6.	Increasing tree and shrub reserves in forest fund areas	mln.m ³	64,2	68,1	77,0	85,5	92,3
7.	Expansion of green spaces in cities (relative to the total area of the settlement) within the framework of the «Green Space» project	%	8,3	12,4	15,8	23,8	30,0
8.	Establishment of 600 new waste collection points in the regions	dona	-	50	200	400	600

The services sector is becoming increasingly important in Uzbekistan in the formation of a “green” economy and ensuring environmental sustainability. As a result of the growing demand for environmentally safe, sustainable and innovative solutions among the population and business entities, the need for “green”

Figure 2. Industries with high demand for “green” business services (%)

The sector of services supporting environmental sustainability and the green economy is expanding, which in turn is leading to the formation of new economic opportunities and a business model based on environmental responsibility. According to the analysis of the presented data, among the areas with the highest demand for “green” business services, “other sectors” (28.9%) are leading. This category is likely to include such diversified activities as transport logistics, eco-technologies, environmental consulting, preservation of blue zones, and climate monitoring. The high demand for services that are compatible with the “green” approach within such a wide range of areas indicates the scale and complexity of the ecological transformation in the market. The waste processing sector is in second place with an indicator of 20.6%, which once again confirms the high demand for this area. This is an important area not only in terms of solving environmental problems, but also in terms of economic efficiency and the creation of secondary resources. Also, “green” transport infrastructure is among the leading areas with a share of 20%. This means that in Uzbekistan, in line with global trends, there is a growing need for low-carbon transport networks - including infrastructure such as electric cars, electric buses, bicycle lanes and optimization of public transport.

The indicators in the areas of recreation services (15.8%) and landscaping (14.7%) indicate an increasing demand for the preservation of green areas, the creation of a healthy ecological environment for the population, and the implementation of the principles of “green” urban planning. These two areas are more related to services such as social infrastructure, ecological design, the transformation of public spaces into green areas, eco-parks and recreation areas, the expansion of which is not only of environmental importance, but also serves the health and well-being of citizens.

It is worth noting that, since the source of these indicators is not specified, it remains unclear whether they are empirical results for Uzbekistan or generalized estimates based on global trends. Accordingly, a cautious and probabilistic interpretation approach should be used when analyzing them. If they reflect the needs at the national level, then the process of cross-sectoral integration of the green economy in Uzbekistan has reached a significant stage. On the contrary, if this is global data, then it can serve as a guide for Uzbekistan in setting priorities, formulating investment policy, and planning personnel training.

Overall, these figures show that the market for “green” business services is integrating not only with traditional environmental sectors, but also with modern sectors such as urbanization, transport and tourism. This once again highlights the need to strengthen cooperation between public policy and the private sector, update the regulatory framework, and encourage environmental innovation.

The transition to a green economy, as well as requiring a fundamental change in the economic model, is also causing a significant increase in the demand for new professions and specialties in the labor market. In this process aimed at ensuring environmental sustainability, there is a shortage of qualified personnel, especially in the technical, engineering and urban development sectors. According to the data provided, the group of specialists in the highest demand today is those working in renewable energy sources, accounting for 17.3% of the total need. This indicator indicates the strategic importance of this sector - personnel for the development of solar, wind and bioenergy technologies are needed not only at the production, but also at the design, monitoring and operation stages.

Figure 3. Specialists in high demand today (%)

In this list, specialists in waste processing and resource reuse are in second place with 15.4%. This indicates that the concept of turning waste into an economic resource is being rapidly implemented. Especially since this area is closely related to the industrial, energy and municipal sectors, the functional role of its specialists is expanding.

Specialties related to urban planning and architecture - namely, urban planner (10.7%) and architect of energy-efficient houses (9.4%) - are also among the important socio-ecological directions. These indicators indicate the need to combine the urbanization process with environmental safety. In the context of environmentally friendly planning, the design of "green" infrastructure and the construction of energy-efficient buildings, the need for specialists in this field is constantly increasing.

Despite the fact that specialists in organic agricultural products (8.3%) and electric vehicle production (8.1%) are among the promising areas of the market, the demand for them at the current stage remains relatively low. However, these areas are in the development stage, and the need for them may increase significantly in the coming years. In particular, in the field of electric vehicle production, there is a shortage of qualified personnel in electrical engineering, battery technology, software control systems, which is also felt globally. It should be noted that the generalized group of "other areas" accounts for 30.8%, which indicates a wide range of professions and specialties needed for a green economy. This area may include environmental engineering, energy management, climate financial consultants, carbon credit system experts, environmental lawyers, environmental impact assessors, reclamation and environmental monitoring specialists. This situation, in turn, indicates the need to develop new professional standards in the labor market and adapt the higher education system to modern environmental needs.

Also, the lack of a clear indication of the source requires a cautious approach to the analysis. Although it is possible that these percentages are taken for the Uzbek labor market, they may also reflect global trends. Therefore, it is recommended to consider these figures as "probable" in the analysis and to further strengthen them through official statistics and industry reports.

Overall, this analysis shows that the green economy is creating a real need for a wide range of interconnected and modern professionals not only in the energy and waste management sectors, but also in urban planning, transport, agriculture and services. This makes it necessary to prepare the personnel training system for the “green” transformation, develop and widely implement advanced training programs.

The transition to a green economy means not only ensuring environmental sustainability, but also moving to a qualitatively new stage of economic growth. However, this transformation does not occur naturally, by itself. In order to systematically and consistently launch the process of green economic growth, a system of effective mechanisms, including clear strategic directions, institutional reforms and financial mechanisms, is necessary. These mechanisms, on the one hand, stimulate the rational use of available resources, and on the other hand, coordinate the activities of the private sector, the state and civil society aimed at sustainable development.

At present, despite the existence of a regulatory framework and programs for the green economy in Uzbekistan, practical effectiveness in many areas remains low. Therefore, in order to increase green growth indicators, it is necessary to develop not only political will and a general strategy, but also a set of clear and practical mechanisms that serve to implement them in the real economy. The priority areas of such mechanisms and their expected results are presented in the table below.

Table 2. Key mechanisms for enhancing green economic growth

Mechanism name	Brief description	Expected result
1. Introduction of green financing mechanisms	Government grants, green bonds, subsidies and preferences for environmental projects	Increasing the investment attractiveness of projects, expanding private sector participation
2. Incentives for decarbonization	Providing tax breaks or carbon credits to businesses that reduce CO ₂ emissions	Reducing waste in industry, reducing carbon footprint
3. Widespread introduction of renewable energy	Subsidizing and technical support for solar, wind, and biogas technologies	Energy independence, reduced carbon emissions
4. «Green» personnel training system	Opening green directions in universities, focusing curricula on environmental competencies	Training qualified specialists needed in the labor market
5. Green standards and regulatory framework	Introduction of environmental standards in the construction, energy and industrial sectors	Sustainable production and environmental safety
6. Development of waste processing infrastructure	Clusters for local waste separation, industrial and household waste recycling	Saving resources, reducing waste
7. Innovation incubations for green technologies	Commercialization of environmental technologies through startups and technoparks	Putting innovations into practice, creating new jobs
8. Development of green transport	Modernization of electric vehicle infrastructure and public transport	Improved urban air quality, reduced fuel imports
9. Efficient use of water resources	Subsidizing drip irrigation technologies and water-saving devices	Preventing water shortages in agriculture
10. Multi-level governance with local authorities	Formation of regional environmental programs, local environmental budgets	Solving environmental problems at the local level

1. Green financing mechanisms: This mechanism, which has not yet been widely implemented in Uzbekistan, reduces risks between investors and the state through financial instruments such as “green bonds” and “stability funds”, based on the experience of the European Union and Asian countries.

2. Incentives for decarbonization: The gradual introduction of a competitive carbon tax or trading system will encourage industry to ecologically renew itself.

3. Widespread introduction of renewable energy: If investment risks are reduced in this direction through state subsidies and technical assistance programs, many private projects will be implemented.

4. Green training: Integrating green competencies into the curricula of universities and vocational schools will ensure the training of specialists in line with market needs.

5. Green standards: Environmental risks will be reduced by using energy-efficient materials in construction and making environmental management standards such as ISO 14001 mandatory.

6. Waste infrastructure: The establishment of local-level recycling plants, waste separation systems, and industrial clusters will ensure resource circulation.

7. Innovation incubation: Special grant programs, startup incubators, and technology parks play an important role in the development and commercialization of eco-technologies.

8. Green transport: The development of electric vehicles and bicycle infrastructure will radically improve the ecology of large cities and reduce the cost of imported fuel.

9. Water resources: The introduction of water-saving technologies in agriculture is of vital importance, especially in the context of climate change.

10. Multi-level governance: It is necessary to expand the powers of local authorities and differentiate budgets in making environmental decisions.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS.

Although important program documents have been adopted and the regulatory and legal framework is being strengthened in the Republic of Uzbekistan on the path to a green economy, a systematic and comprehensive approach to this area is necessary to increase practical effectiveness. The results of the study show that the energy, construction, transport, agriculture and waste management sectors are of priority importance in the development of a green economy. At the same time, the growing demand for ecological specialties in the labor market indicates the need to improve the system of training personnel with knowledge and skills related to the introduction of modern green technologies. Significant progress can be made towards sustainable development by using the existing potential in the country, in particular solar and wind energy resources, opportunities for transition to environmentally friendly production, and the adoption of international experience.

To increase green economic growth indicators, it is important to introduce specific mechanisms in the financial, institutional, technological and educational spheres. In particular, mechanisms such as creating favorable conditions for environmental investments, providing tax incentives for enterprises that reduce carbon emissions, subsidizing renewable energy sources, developing waste processing infrastructure, forming a “green” transport infrastructure, as well as developing and implementing environmental standards will ensure not only economic efficiency, but also social and environmental sustainability. In this regard, it is necessary to increase initiative at the level of local authorities, strengthen financing of regional environmental projects and monitoring systems. In conclusion, in order for Uzbekistan’s strategy for transition to a green economy to achieve real results, it is necessary to conduct state policy not only on the basis of declarative, but also on the basis of a practical and cross-sectoral integrated approach, and to mobilize existing opportunities through effective mechanisms. This will be an important step towards protecting the interests of not only today, but also future generations.

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